

IMPORTANCE OF BILINGUALISM IN EARLY AGES

Termez state university

Department of Foreign filology, Teacher

Mavlanova Gulnigor Baxriddin kizi

Department of Foreign filology, Student

Xayitaliyeva Sarvinoz Abdurayimovna

sarvialiyeva03@gmail.com

Annotation. Majority of the people around the world being affected by dual-language environments from an early ages, consequently this results in becoming bilingual. Also there are positive and negative sides that we discussed and dismantled some of the ways to increase the productive outcome.

Key words: Bilingualism, Bilingual children, dual-language environment, positive and negative impacts, myths, misinterpretation, productive outcome, strategies.

Annotatsiya. Dunyo bo'ylab odamlarning ko'pchiligi erta yoshdanoq ikki tilli muhit ta'siriga tushib qolishmoqda, natijada bu ikki tilli bo'lishga olib keladi. Tabiiyki, buning o'ziga yarasha ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari ham bor va biz samarali natijani oshirishning ba'zi usullarini muhokama qildik.

Tayanch so'zlar: Ikki tillilik, ikki tilli bolalar, ikki tilli muhit, ijobiy va salbiy ta'sirlar, afsonalar, noto'g'ri talqin qilish, samarali natija, strategiyalar.

Bilingualism is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that has been extensively studied across various academic disciplines such as philosophy, linguistics, and psychology. In essence, bilingualism refers to the ability to use or speak two languages. According to the Cambridge Dictionary, bilingualism is defined as the fact of using or being able to speak two languages [1]. However, it is important to note that there are many definitions of bilingualism, each with its own nuances and variations. For instance, U. Weinreich calls "bilingual practice the alternate use of two languages" [2] while Rosenzweig defines "Bilingualism is usually understood as the possession of two languages, regular switching from one to another depending on the situation of communication" [3].

Bilingualism is common and is on the rise in many parts of the world, with perhaps one in three people being bilingual or multilingual [4]. Nowadays, more of the world's population is bilingual or multilingual than monolingual [5] which means that many children grow up exposed to two or more languages from an early age or learned

second language. In the current period, when the mixture of peoples, languages and cultures has reached unprecedented scope, and more than ever the problem of raising tolerance for foreign cultures, awakening interest and respect for others and this makes bilingualism in intercultural communication extremely significant. In the same city can live a few dozen or hundreds of different nationalities who have not forgotten their native language which signifies that contact between two languages is typical in regions of many continents, including Europe, Asia, Africa and North America [6]. In neighboring regions, near the borders, the number of people speaking two languages is growing. In some countries (Switzerland, Canada) the people who can communicate freely in two or three languages make up a large number. In the United States, a large (and growing) number of bilinguals live in California, Texas, Florida, New York, Arizona, and New Mexico. In California, for example, by 2035, it is expected that over 50% of children enrolled in kindergarten will have grown up speaking a language other than English (García, McLaughlin, Spodek, & Saracho, 1995) [6]. Similarly, in some urban areas of Canada such as Toronto, up to 50% of students have a native language other than English (Canadian Council on Learning, 2008) [7].

Learning, however, second language and being grown up in bilingual environment is different situations. One way to think about bilingualism is to think about *when* a person learned the language. If you've learned multiple languages since birth, you can be considered a simultaneous bilingual. Some simultaneous bilinguals are exposed to a different language from each parent, and for others there may be another person at home, like a grandparent, who uses a particular language with them. Learning 2 languages from birth may not mean the person continues to use both languages consistently throughout their life, or even just throughout their childhood. But this exposure to 2 languages at once, right from the start, creates a special task for your baby brain. Many parents concerned about the cost and benefits of raising children in dual-language environment, also there some myths that causes parents of toddlers and infants worry about if early bilingualism confuses their children and holds back their development. Some Research Perspectives have proved that being able to speak in two languages is normal case and it is not always means that bilinguals from early ages always fluent in all languages that they know. We can see more detailly about misconceptions and types of bilingualism in one of the articles by Kent Lee:

1. Misconceptions

Many myths abound about bilingualism and multilingualism, e.g.:

- that bi-/multilinguals are exceptions, and that monolingualism is the norm
- that they necessarily must be equally perfect or native-like in both languages
- that childhood exposure to two or more languages can limit or hinder linguistic development or cognitive development and consequently lead to poorer results at school
- that exposure to multiple languages in childhood may make children confused.

The truth is, in fact, that much psychological research shows cognitive advantages of bilingualism, for adults and especially for children. Children are not necessarily confused when they switch between languages. This is a normal pattern among child and adult language learners known as code-switching or code-mixing, and it occurs for various reasons, particularly for reasons of social context and for expressive reasons[8].

2.Types

Scholars have distinguished a number of different types of bilingualism, based on various criteria, and there is no single accepted definition of bilingualism that is scientifically precise. Instead, one must speak of different types and degrees of bilingualism, depending on age of acquisition, means or manner of acquisition, degree of proficiency, and sociolinguistic factors [9,10].

- Early vs. late bilingualism
- Early simultaneous vs. successive bilingualism - depending on whether the second language was learned early or later
- Balanced vs. dominant bilingualism
- Compound, coordinate, and subordinate bilingualism - depending on how the languages are mentally stored, accessed, and processed with respect to each other
- Folk vs. elite bilingualism, depending on the social status of the languages

Furthermore, E.M.Vereshagin distinguishes three levels of bilingualism: receptive (a type of bilingualism in which an individual who speaks a second language understands it, although he cannot synthesize text in a given language), reproductive (an individual can reproduce what he read and heard in that language on which he

perceived them) and productive (the ability not only to understand and reproduce, but "to make up meaningful statements") [11].

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